

Survey paper

Emotion recognition systems with electrodermal activity: From affective science to affective computing

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ABSTRACT

Affective computing is an interdisciplinary field that aims to automatically recognize and interpret emotions. Recent research has focused on using physiological signals (e.g., electrodermal activity) to improve emotion recognition. However, the theoretical emotion models that underlie these systems have received comparatively little attention. We conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis on electrodermal-activity-based emotion-recognition systems. Our findings suggest that arousal prediction models outperform valence prediction models, supporting our preregistered hypothesis. This correlates with arousal's association with autonomic nervous system activity and its direct link to electrodermal activity. We also observed a mismatch between the machine-learning approaches most often used—chiefly classification models—and the predominantly dimensional emotion frameworks adopted in the literature. Specifically, although dimensional affective models are increasingly popular, there has not been a parallel rise in regression models that would better reflect the continuous nature of the underlying data. We conclude that a comprehensive understanding of affective states requires consideration of both psychological and computational perspectives in affective computing research.

1. Introduction

Affective computing, which emerged in the 1990s, is a growing interdisciplinary field aiming at incorporating emotions into artificial intelligence [1]. Researchers in this field combine affective science, computer science and engineering methods not only to advance the scientific understanding of human emotions but also to develop technologies that can effectively operate in emotionally nuanced contexts [2–4]. A particular interest lies in the development of methods and algorithms for automatically recognizing and interpreting affective states [5]. These advancements in affective computing hold significant

promise, opening up transformative applications across a range of fields such as healthcare [6], education [7,8], and self-driving cars [9].

To enable these applications, affective computing models rely on various forms of input to predict human emotions accurately. Traditionally, these models have used observable signals such as facial expressions [10], posture [11], speech [12], thermography [13], and text [14]. More recently, however, there has been a growing interest in utilizing physiological signals because they are readily available, believed to be less sensitive to social and cultural variability [15] and allow for continuous sampling of participants' physiological activity [16].

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These physiological signals can be particularly informative when interpreted through the lens of affective science, which provides the theoretical foundation for understanding emotions in affective computing. Specifically, the study of emotions in this field relies on various theoretical models that can be broadly divided into two categories: categorical and dimensional models. Categorical models, like Ekman's, propose discrete emotional states (e.g., happiness, sadness, fear, anger) [17,18], and are widely used in classification tasks. Dimensional models, especially Russell's circumplex model [19,20], represent emotions along continuous scales, such as valence (positive to negative affect) and arousal (level of physiological activation), aligning closely with physiological measures.

The increasing use of these physiological measures has led to the use of statistical and computational tools to interpret complex emotional data [21]. In particular, the application of machine learning to affective computing has opened new avenues for predicting and understanding affective states [22]. Most of the publications focused on supervised learning, which operates by training on a set of known data and corresponding labels, essentially learning the underlying relationships between them [23]. The resulting models are practical for summarizing complex psychophysiological datasets into scores, and can be used for making predictions on new data points (see Fig. 1). Given the reliance on physiological data in affective computing, understanding the sources and types of physiological signals available becomes essential.

Physiological signals can be broadly divided into central and peripheral measures. Central measures, such as electroencephalograms (EEG), focus on capturing brain activity, while peripheral measures, including electrocardiography (ECG), electromyography (EMG), electrooculography (EOG), and electrodermal activity (EDA), record activity from the peripheral nervous system. Importantly, peripheral measures are closely linked to emotional responses because they record interoceptive feedback from various systems (including the stress, neuroendocrine, immune, and gastrointestinal systems) that strongly influence our subjective emotional experiences [24].

EDA holds unique value as a peripheral measure in emotion recognition. Renowned for its ease of use and accessibility [25], EDA is widely regarded as a robust proxy for emotional arousal, as it is innervated by the sympathetic branch of the autonomic nervous system [26]. Formerly known as the galvanic skin response, EDA measures changes in skin's electrical properties triggered by the activity of sweat glands, specifically the sudomotor neurons [26]. These glands, while primarily functioning in thermoregulation, are especially active in the palms and soles during states of high emotional arousal, regardless of valence [27]. This includes both negative emotions such as fear or stress, and positive

emotions like excitement or joy. However, the relationship between EDA and valence—whether the emotional experience is positive or negative—is more complex and requires further exploration. Therefore, EDA serves as a reliable indicator primarily of arousal in affective science [26] and for detecting affective dimensions in affective computing [28].

Given its unique properties, EDA has demonstrated practical utility across various applied settings. In the context of assisted driving, for instance, real-time monitoring of a driver's arousal can improve safety by detecting states of heightened stress, drowsiness, or distraction [29]. EDA-based emotion recognition is also being incorporated into healthcare applications, such as stress detection systems [30] and biofeedback therapies [31], due to its sensitivity to autonomic responses that may reflect emotional intensity.

Recently, substantial efforts have been directed towards enhancing the predictive capabilities of emotion recognition models using EDA signals, as highlighted in reviews by [32] and [33]. Review [32] primarily focuses on EDA data collection and signal processing techniques, providing a summary of advancements in EDA measurement. Review [33], on the other hand, centers around feature extraction techniques from EDA signals, analyzing different features across time, frequency, and time-frequency domains for emotion recognition tasks. However, despite these methodological aspects already covered in the literature, there has been a notable gap regarding the underlying affective components employed in EDA-based emotion recognition systems.

Addressing a critical but often overlooked aspect, we conduct an in-depth systematic review and meta-analysis with a primary focus on investigating the underlying emotion models used in EDA-based emotion recognition systems. Our review also examines the characteristics of self-reported emotion models, the sample, and the techniques used for emotion stimulation. In addition, we evaluate machine learning models and various EDA parameters, such as equipment and locations, commonly used in automatic emotion recognition tasks. Moreover, our review identifies the challenges associated with different emotional induction techniques and provides recommendations for standardizing approaches in future studies. Finally, we aim to establish a link between the affective science and affective computing literatures by comparing the performance of arousal and valence prediction models using EDA. Based on the established relationship between arousal, autonomic nervous system activity, and EDA, we hypothesize that arousal prediction models would typically outperform valence prediction models. By fostering interdisciplinarity and emphasizing the integration of psychological perspectives with computational models, we aim to pave the way for more robust and physiologically valid approaches to EDA-based

Fig. 1. End-to-end pipeline for predicting emotions from electrodermal activity (EDA). (A) Data collection. Participants wear an EDA sensor while performing an affect-evoking task. Each record in the dataset (sample 1, 2, ..., n) contains a raw EDA time series paired with the participant's self-reported emotion on a scale. (B) Model training. After optional preprocessing (e.g. artefact removal, downsampling and normalization) and feature engineering, the EDA signal is fed into a machine learning model that learns to map physiological patterns onto the corresponding affective reports. (C) Model testing. The trained network is evaluated on previously unseen data; predicted emotion labels are compared with the ground truth reports to quantify performance (green check mark = correct classification, red cross = misclassification).

emotion recognition in affective computing.

2. Methods

The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) protocol [34,35] was used in this systematic review to ensure the replicability of the study (<http://prisma-statement.org>).

2.1. Preregistration

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in interest and concern for reproducibility in science [36]. To follow good open science practices and avoid publication bias, the planned study was registered in the Open Science Framework (OSF) web repository prior to implementation (see <https://osf.io/zbqmq6>). For example, the hypothesis that arousal prediction models would perform better than valence prediction models was preregistered in this document.

2.2. Eligibility criteria

In our review, we included studies that used machine learning techniques for emotion recognition using EDA. For the purposes of this review, a machine learning model is defined as the use of statistical models to estimate functions algorithmically for making predictions or

decisions. This estimation aims to minimize generalization error for better out-of-sample prediction. We incorporate simple linear models, such as penalized logistic regression, as well as advanced techniques like deep learning models, which possess the added capability of learning features automatically. Each unique model from every article was included as a separate instance for evaluation if they differed in any of the variables of interest in the review, such as dataset, algorithm, or type of output. For the descriptive synthesis we retained only the best-performing model within each feature set; however, all models were included in the meta-analysis to avoid selection bias. Finally, our study was restricted to English-written articles that examined non-clinical human samples.

Exclusion criteria included master's and doctoral theses, book chapters as non-peer-reviewed literature, reviews, meta-analyses, commentaries, workshops, descriptions and abstracts. Studies that included only models trained on multimodal signals (e.g., EDA and heart rate variability) were also excluded. However, if different models were trained in the same paper, and one or more used only EDA features, they were included for further analysis. Finally, papers that created software tools (unless they were emotion recognition software and tested according to the criteria established in this review) were not included in this review.

Fig. 2. PRISMA flowchart summarizing study selection for the systematic review and meta-analysis. The diagram tracks the literature search from initial identification of 1595 database records (Scopus and PubMed) through duplicate removal, title/abstract screening, and full-text eligibility assessment. At each stage, articles were excluded according to predefined criteria (e.g., non-EDA modality, clinical cohorts, language restrictions), with specific numbers and reasons listed in the sidebars. This process resulted in 181 studies for qualitative synthesis and a subset of 35 studies reporting sufficient quantitative metrics for inclusion in the meta-analysis. n = number of articles.

2.3. Search strategy and selection process

Scopus and PubMed were used to identify journal articles, conferences, and preprints published between January 1, 2010, and February 11, 2025. If articles exist in both versions, preference was given to publications that have been peer-reviewed after preprinting. The flowchart from this review can be found in Fig. 2.

A comprehensive search strategy was employed in the Scopus and PubMed databases to exhaustively retrieve all relevant papers that satisfy our inclusion criteria. The following keywords and Boolean operators were used: “EDA” OR “Electrodermal Activity” OR “GSR” OR “Galvanic Skin Response” OR “Skin conductance” OR “SCR” OR “SCL” AND “Emotions” OR “Emotion” OR “Affective” AND “Recognition” OR “Decoding” OR “Detection” OR “Classification” OR “Regression”. The search terms were applied to the title, abstract, and keywords. The advanced search criteria included: “between 2010–2025; journal, conference proceeding as source type; article, conference paper as document type; and English as language”. This search was conducted on February 11, 2025.

To ensure the comprehensiveness of our search, an iterative process was adopted whereby the search strategy was refined and re-run until all known relevant papers were identified in the search results. Additionally, we manually screened the reference lists of included papers to identify further potential studies not captured by our search strategy, reducing the likelihood of missing relevant research.

Once the papers were identified, they were exported to the Rayyan tool [37] to streamline the initial selection process. The investigators (cf. section *CRedit authorship contribution statement*) divided the total number of papers among themselves and eliminated duplicates. The authors checked the titles, abstracts, and keywords for discrepancies based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and double-checked the classifications made by the other authors, which were randomly assigned. The number of excluded papers and the reasons for their exclusion were documented in Rayyan.

The remaining papers were then exported to Zotero [38], a free open-source software and web management tool. The investigating author read the full papers, discarding those that did not meet the inclusion criteria. During multiple readings, specific dimensions were identified, and papers that did not fulfill these dimensions were discarded at each step.

2.4. Data collection process

For the papers that met the criteria, a subset of the authors was designated to conduct the data extraction. Each designated author retrieved the data from all the recognition models found in their assigned articles. These models were classified into nine categories for further analysis (see *Data Elements* section). Subsequently, a second designated author, different from the first, reviewed the classifications to ensure consistency and accuracy. Any disagreements or conflicts in the classifications were addressed in a joint meeting with a third author, who served as a mediator if necessary.

2.5. Data elements

A shared database was created among the authors, where each paper was classified according to the following criteria: metadata (data on the authors, title, year of publication, journal in which it was published, type of article, country of affiliation of the first author); type of data (original or from database, if the latter, specify which); participants (relevant characteristics of the sample: size, gender, age range, country of origin, etc.); affective stimulation technique (type of affective stimulus used, exposure time); self-report (if used, what type used, emotion model used); EDA (equipment used, location of sensors); statistical learning models (output of model used, type of model); emotion model and performance of emotion recognition models with EDA. This

database is openly available in a GitHub repository (see the *Supplementary Material* section).

2.6. Study Risk of Bias Assessment

Each paper in each round was double-checked by two different authors for discrepancies in classification and inclusion using the Rayyan and Zotero tools. If discrepancies existed, they were noted and resolved with a third member of the team.

2.7. Meta-analysis

In conducting a meta-analysis to compare the performance of valence and arousal recognition models in emotion recognition, we followed a comprehensive, systematic protocol consisting of several key steps.

Our first step was to define the scope of our meta-analysis by establishing strict inclusion and exclusion criteria. A critical requirement was that studies use accuracy as a measure of performance—an indicator that is widely used across models. We prioritized studies that used binary classification models that produced distinct output categories (i.e., low vs. high valence, and low vs. high arousal). Because our goal was to conduct a comparative analysis of arousal versus valence, we only included studies that examined models of both dimensions, hence, excluding those that were limited to a single affective dimension. All models trained, tested and reported in each of the publications were included for further analysis.

We extracted data from the selected studies. Details such as the machine learning model used, and performance scores were carefully transcribed to ensure that data for arousal and valence models were clearly separated.

Permutation and bootstrap tests were used for null-hypothesis significance testing and uncertainty estimation, respectively, for the observed differences in accuracy between arousal and valence. These tests were chosen for their simplicity and robustness to assumptions about the underlying data distribution. The number of resamples for both permutation and bootstrap tests was kept at the software’s default of 9999.

Finally, we conducted multiple regression analyses using both ordinary least squares (OLS) and robust regression with Huber’s T norm. These analyses were conducted to explore the influence of model architecture, database characteristics, and control variables (i.e. sample size, publication year, and mean accuracy) on the differences in accuracy between arousal and valence classification. The model included dummy variables for different model families and databases, along with continuous predictors for sample size, publication year, and mean accuracy. This comprehensive approach allowed us to assess the relative contribution of each factor to the observed performance gap.

2.8. Software

Quantitative analyses were conducted using the Python programming language [39], supplemented by specialized libraries such as NumPy [40], SciPy [41], Matplotlib [42], pandas [43], and statsmodels [44]. Results will be summarized in narrative, tabular, or graphical form.

3. Results

3.1. Screening and selection

Our systematic review procedure, outlined in Fig. 2, includes the detailed enumeration of discarded articles, the respective reasons for their exclusion, and the final selection of articles retained for further analysis. Through rigorous evaluation, we refined our corpus to a set of 181 studies, providing a comprehensive landscape of 1033 different

emotion prediction models for our subsequent in-depth analysis.

3.2. Data analysis

3.2.1. Geographical distribution and source of publications

The predominance in the distribution of articles lies with China, contributing 31 articles. This is followed by researchers in India (n = 26 articles), the USA (n = 14), and Germany (n = 9). Researchers in Malaysia, Spain, and Canada each produced 7 articles, while Italy and Switzerland contributed 6 apiece. Turkey, Pakistan, the United Kingdom, and South Korea accounted for 5 articles each; Iran for 4; and Romania, Taiwan, Portugal, Greece, and Japan for 3 each. Countries including Austria, Finland, Tunisia, New Zealand, Colombia, Slovenia, France, Macedonia, the United Arab Emirates, and Australia are represented with two articles each. A variety of other countries—Indonesia, Lithuania, Egypt, the Netherlands, Poland, Ireland, Saudi Arabia, Norway, and Sweden—complete the distribution (see Fig. 3).

Within Italy and Malaysia, a significant portion of the articles came from specific research groups; for example, a single group in Italy produced 4 of 6 papers, demonstrating this group's leading position within the Italian scientific community, and in Malaysia 6 of 7 papers originated from one research group.

On the continental scale, Asia stands at the forefront, contributing most articles, totaling 93. This is followed by Europe, with a contribution of 58 articles. The Americas offered 23 articles, while Oceania and Africa rounded off the diversity with 4 and 3 articles, respectively. We also analyzed the sources of these academic papers. The majority were journal articles (n = 104), followed by conference papers (n = 76) and a single preprint (n = 1).

Of the journal-based papers, most were published in engineering and computer science journals. Sensors accounted for the largest share (n = 12), followed by IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing (n = 9). IEEE Access and Biomedical Signal Processing and Control each contributed five articles, whereas IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics and Frontiers in Neuroscience published four apiece. Three articles were published in both Electronics (Switzerland) and the IEEE Sensors Journal. Seven journals (Frontiers in ICT, Studies in Health

Technology and Informatics, Scientific Reports, Expert Systems with Applications, IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement, Frontiers in Psychology, and Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies) contributed two papers each. The remaining 45 articles were dispersed across 45 additional journals, each represented by a single publication.

3.2.2. Data type

We categorized the databases used in the studies into two types: "restricted" databases, which were limited to the use of a specific study, and "open" databases, which were accessible to the public. Out of the 181 recorded database usages, 49.72 % relied on open databases, 48.07 % on restricted databases, and 2.21 % used both.

Nonetheless, a trend towards open databases has been observed over time, as illustrated in Fig. 4A.

Among the publicly accessible databases, 25.56 % came from DEAP [45], 24.44 % from AMIGOS [46], 14.44 % from MAHNOB-HCI [47], and 10 % from CASE [48]. Other databases were used less frequently, as shown in Fig. 4B. Please see Table 1 for further database details.

3.2.3. Participants

For the studies reviewed, the median sample size was 30 participants (mean = 52.2), with values ranging from 4 to 1200. It is noteworthy that 9 studies (4.9 %) did not report sample size, and were therefore excluded from the meta-analysis. When considering gender representation, we noted that 18.8 % of the papers (n = 34) did not report the gender distribution of their samples. In the remaining studies (n = 147), women represented on average 44.6 % of participants, with female counts ranging from 0 to 574. Age information was not provided in 31 papers (17.1 %). For the studies that did report age, the mean of reported mean ages was 26.3 years, with values ranging from 5 to 44.2 years; of these, 29.5 % failed to specify the corresponding age range. The geographical diversity of the participants was also considered, although only 27.6 % of the papers (n = 50) reported the country of origin of their samples.

Fig. 3. Geographical distribution of studies on emotion recognition from electrodermal activity (EDA). The choropleth map aggregates the studies retained after systematic screening (see Fig. 2) according to the country of affiliation of the first author. Shading follows a sequential blue palette: light blue = one article; darkest blue = 31 articles (China, the largest contributor). Circles indicate the exact number of articles for each contributing nation, while countries with no eligible publications remain gray.

Fig. 4. Accessibility trends and dataset preferences in electrodermal activity (EDA) emotion recognition studies. (A) Temporal evolution of dataset accessibility (2010–2025). Each stacked bar represents the within-year proportion of studies relying on (blue) open-access datasets, (orange) restricted datasets, or (green) a combination of both. The bars are normalized to 100 % to emphasize changes in relative rather than absolute use. The profile shows an early dominance of restricted datasets and a steady adoption of open repositories starting in 2013. (B) Popularity of specific EDA emotion databases. Bars indicate how many of the 181 studies reviewed used each database (shown only if cited in > 1 study). DEAP and AMIGOS together account for nearly a third of all database selections, followed by MAHNOB, CASE, ASCERTAIN and WESAD.

3.2.4. Self-report

In relation to affective questionnaires utilized in the studies, we found that 28.6 % of the papers did not use or specify any instrument. Conversely, 65.4 % reported an affective questionnaire, and 5.9 % relied on questionnaires developed in other studies.

Within the studies that specified an instrument, the Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM; [49]) was the most common, being employed in 77.0 % of cases ($n = 94$). The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS; [50]) appeared in 18.9 % of cases ($n = 23$). Less frequently used questionnaires included the Affective Grid [51] ($n = 2$ papers), the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS; [52], $n = 2$ papers), and the Differential Emotion Scale (DES; [53], $n = 1$ paper).

The large amount of missing information, especially regarding participant demographics and questionnaire use, will be addressed in the Discussion section.

3.2.5. Relationships between emotional categories and dimensions

Emotional categorization and dimensional representation are the two primary perspectives employed in affective research. In our review we identified 34 emotional categories in studies using self-report measures. The terminology mirrors that of the original studies and ranges from discrete emotions such as “Disgust” and “Fear” to broader states such as “Stress”. The most frequently cited categories were “Anger”, “Disgust”, “Sadness”, “Fear”, “Neutral”, and “Surprise”, as depicted in Fig. 5A. Other categories appeared far less often.

Emotional dimensions were likewise reported. Thirteen dimensions were identified: “Valence”, “Arousal”, “Dominance”, “Like/Dislike”, “Familiarity”, “Predictability”, and seven other less-frequent dimensions. Notably, “Valence” and “Arousal” were by far the most prevalent, whereas “Dominance”, “Like/Dislike”, and “Familiarity” appeared markedly less often (Fig. 5B).

To provide a more granular perspective, we generated two graphs showcasing relationships between various categories and dimensions (Figs. 5C and 5D). Understanding these relationships is essential for constructing a comprehensive picture of emotional states in the reviewed studies.

3.2.6. Emotion elicitation techniques

Emotion elicitation plays a central role in affective research. Our findings suggest that standardized techniques were employed in 17.1 % of studies ($n = 31$). The most common was IAPS (International Affective Picture System; [54], $n = 14$, 7.7 %), followed by the Trier Social Stress Test (TSST; [55], $n = 11$, 6.1 %). The Stroop color-word interference test (SCWT; [56]), Rapid-ABC play protocol [57], International Affective Digitized Sound (IADS; [58]), Robin [59], and the Modified Autobiographical Memory Test (AMT) [60] each appeared in one study.

We also found a significant preference for multimodal strategies, with 67.3 % of studies using such methods. Among specific techniques, video was the most common (51.3 %), followed by music (11.3 %) and pictures (11.3 %).

Table 1
Publicly-available datasets for emotion-recognition studies based on EDA.

Dataset	Citation	N	Gender (% F)	Age	Location	Purpose	EDA device	Signals	Affective annotation	Stimuli	Link
DEAP	[45]	32	50 %	19–37 (mean = 26.9)	Twente (Netherlands) and Geneva (Switzerland)	To facilitate the advancement of emotion analysis methods using a multimodal dataset incorporating physiological signals.	BioSemi ActiveTwo	EDA, EEG, EOG, EMG, BVP, Resp, Temp, Video	SAM with dimensions: valence, arousal, dominance. Other self-assessments: like/dislike, and familiarity	40 one-minute long excerpts of music video	https://www.eecs.qmul.ac.uk/mmv/datasets/deap/
AMIGOS	[46]	40	32.5 %	21–40 (mean = 28.3)	UK	To enable multimodal research on affect, personality traits and mood in individuals and groups, allowing the analysis of emotional responses across different social contexts and video durations.	Shimmer 2 R	EDA, EEG, ECG, Video, Audio	PANAS and self-assessments with dimensions: valence, arousal, dominance, like/dislike, familiarity. Basic emotions: anger, disgust, fear, sadness, surprise, happiness, and neutral	Sixteen short videos and four long videos	http://www.eecs.qmul.ac.uk/mmv/datasets/amigos/index.html
MAHNOB-HCI	[47]	27	56.7 %	19–40 (mean = 26.1)	London (UK)	Promote exploration of non-verbal dimensions in human communication, emotion recognition and implicit tagging	BioSemi ActiveTwo	EDA, EEG, ECG, Video, Audio, Eye-gaze, Resp, Temp	Self-assessment with dimensions: valence, arousal, dominance and predictability.	Twenty videos between 34.9 and 117 s long	https://mahnob-db.eu/
ASCERTAIN	[105]	58	36.2 %	mean 30	N/A	Simultaneous personality-trait and affect recognition using commercial sensors.	Commercial Bluetooth sensor	EDA, EEG, ECG, Video	Dimensions: valence, arousal, engagement, liking and familiarity	Thirty-six movie clips. The average length is 80 s	https://ascertain-dataset.github.io/
MMDB	[106]	121	N/A	15–30 m	US	To support the study and modeling of social behavior, emotion, and nonverbal communication in dyadic adult-child interactions	Affectiva Q sensor	EDA, Video, Audio	17 binary-coded child behaviors (present/absent) plus a 0–2 Likert scale rating of examiner effort to engage the child.	Five-minute social interaction scenarios	https://cbs.ic.gatech.edu/mmdb/
RECOLA	[107]	46	58.7 %	mean = 22 (SD = 3)	Fribourg (Switzerland)	To enable real-time analysis of emotional responses in social interaction scenarios	BIOPAC MP36	EDA, ECG, Video, Audio	SAM with dimensions: valence and arousal. And PANAS	Twenty-three teams were given a collaborative task that elicited social and emotional behaviors (~15 min length)	https://qualinet.github.io/databases/audiovisual/recola/
PMEmo	[108]	457	51.6 %	N/A	Hangzhou (China)	To capture and analyze individual emotional expressions using a multimodal data set collected from multiple sources.	BIOPAC MP150	EDA	SAM with dimensions: valence and arousal	794 music clips	https://github.com/HuiZhanGDB/PMEmo
Hazumi1911	[109]	26	50 %	20–70	N/A	To improve the understanding of human-computer interaction by studying communication methods and interpreting multimodal signals and expressions	Empatica e4	EDA, HR, Video, Audio	Self-annotation: enjoy / not-enjoy; external annotation: enjoy / bored	Human-agent interaction dialogues.	https://github.com/ouktlab/Hazumi1911/
BioVid Emo DB	[80]	86	53.2	18–65	Germany	To analyze human affective states and emotions	Nexus–32	EDA, EMG, ECG, Video	Self-assessment: valence, arousal, amusement, sadness, anger, disgust and fear.	Films clips (length: between 32 and 245 s)	N/A

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Table 1 (continued)

Dataset	Citation	N	Gender (% F)	Age	Location	Purpose	EDA device	Signals	Affective annotation	Stimuli	Link
Continuous LIRIS-ACCEDE	[110]	10	30 %	18–27 (mean = 21.9)	France	To facilitate researchers and practitioners with a comprehensive and diverse collection of video data for various computer vision and multimedia tasks.	Bodymedia armband	EDA	Continuous arousal annotations	30 movies (6 different genres and 5 languages). Total duration: ~7 h	https://liris-accede.ec-lyon.fr/database.php
WESAD	[111]	15	20 %	mean = 27.5 ± 2.4	Germany	To provide a high-quality multimodal database that allows the detection and analysis of stress and affective states through wearable devices.	Empatica e4 and RespiBAN Professional	EDA, BVP, ECG, EMG, Resp, Temp, ACC	PANAS, SAM, SSSQ and STAI	4 conditions: baseline (20 min), amusement (392 s video), stress (TSST, ≈10 min), meditation (7 min)	https://github.com/WJMatthew/WESAD
CASE	[48]	30	50 %	22–37 (mean = 27.15)	Germany	To provide high-quality continuous annotations of valence and arousal alongside physiological signals for emotion analysis in realistic video-based settings, using a joystick-based interface.	Thought Technology SA9309M	EDA, ECG, BVP, Resp, Temp, EMG	Continuous annotation of valence and arousal	Eight validated video clips designed to elicit amusement, boredom, relaxation, or fear (length: between 119 and 197 s)	https://gitlab.com/karan-shr/case_dataset
CLAS	[124]	62	27.4 %	20–50	Bulgaria	To support research on the automated recognition of specific states of mind (negative emotions, cognitive load, stress), and to aid in the development of intelligent HCL/HRI systems.	Shimmer3	EDA, ECG, PPG, ACC	Self-assessment with dimensions: valence and arousal	16 video clips (from DEAP), 16 pictures (from IAPS), Math test, Stroop test, Logic test	https://iee-data-port.org/open-access/database-cognitive-load-affect-and-stress-recognition
PAFEW	[125]	24	66.7 %	mean = 24	China	To create a physiological dataset corresponding to the AFEW video dataset for recognizing seven basic emotions (Anger, Disgust, Fear, Happy, Surprise, Sad, Neutral) using physiological signals, with a focus on electrodermal activity (EDA) and the enhancement of emotion recognition models.	Empatica e4	EDA, Temp, PPG, HR, inter-beat intervals EDA, Pupil information	Relies on Dhall et al. [126] self-assessment	1809 movie clips (from AFEW), across 7 emotion classes (length between 300 ms and 5400 ms)	N/A
BioVid Heat Pain	[127]	90	50 %	18–65	Germany	To advance the development and systematic validation of an automated pain recognition system by collecting a multimodal dataset (biopotentials + video) that captures different levels of induced heat pain and emotional responses, aiming to identify relevant features for pain recognition and its dissociation from emotion	NeXus-32	EDA, ECG, EMG, EEG, Video	Self-assessment with dimensions: valence and arousal. Discrete emotions: anger, disgust, fear, sadness, joy	Exposure to four calibrated levels of heat-induced pain using a thermode. Besides, emotional responses were elicited through pictures (from IAPS), short video clips representing basic emotions, and guided posing of facial expressions.	https://www.nit.ovgu.de/nit/en/BioVid-p-1358.html

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Table 1 (continued)

Dataset	Citation	N	Gender (% F)	Age	Location	Purpose	EDA device	Signals	Affective annotation	Stimuli	Link
K-EmoCon	[128]	32	37.5 %	19–36 (mean = 23.8)	South Korea	To support continuous emotion recognition in naturalistic social interactions by providing multimodal data and annotations from multiple perspectives (self, partner, external) during debates.	Empatica e4	EDA, EEG, ECG, HR, BVP, Temp, ACC, Audio, Video	Retrospective affect judgment from three perspectives (self, partner, external observers) of dimensions: valence and arousal. Discrete emotions: cheerful, nervous, boredom, confusion, delight, engaged concentration, frustration, confrustion, contempt, dejection, eureka, pride, sorrow, happiness, surprise, sadness, disgust, anger	10-minute semi-structured debates on a social issue (accepting Yemeni refugees in Jeju Island, South Korea), after being provided with preparatory readings (two neutral, one pro, one against).	https://zenodo.org/records/3931963
VREED	[129]	34	50 %	18–61 (mean = 25)	UK	To provide a publicly available multimodal affective dataset using Virtual Reality (VR) to study emotion recognition based on behavioral and physiological measures.	Biopac mp150	EDA, Eye-gaze, ECG	SAM with dimensions: valence and arousal; Self-assessment for joy, happiness, calmness, relaxation, anger, disgust, fear, anxiousness, sadness, dizziness	Immersive 360° videos delivered in VR (length between 1 and 3 min)	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/e9e93acd547401db81cd9988c96760d823142fa894a4a79c6af971949d4bdf85
Affective Road	[130]	10	50 %	24–59 (mean = 29.9)	Tunisia	To develop and validate a context-aware system for monitoring the driver's physiological and environmental states during real-world driving using wearable and ambient sensors.	Empatica e4	EDA, BVP, Temp, ACC, Resp, ECG, Audio, Video, Humidity, Pressure, Luminosity	Continuous stress/arousal metric ranging from 0 to 1 was generated in real-time by the experimenter using a slider, based on perceived workload. This was later validated and corrected by participants via synchronized video playback of the driving session.	Naturalistic driving protocol (31 km; ≈ 1 h 26 min), including high-stress urban areas (narrow streets, red lights, pedestrians), highways, and rest periods.	N/A
UTD	[131]	20	30 %	19–33 (mean = 25.6)	US	To encourage other researchers to extract new knowledge out of prerecorded biosignals from different neurological statuses	Affectiva	EDA, ACC, HR, Blood oxygen level	N/A	Four types of tasks: Physical stress (stand for a minute, walk for two minutes, jog for two minutes); Cognitive stress (Counting backwards by sevens for three minutes and Stroop for two minutes); Emotional stress (five-minute horror clip); and Relaxation (five minutes between each of the other blocks)	https://personal.utdallas.edu/~nourani/Bioinformatics/Biosensor_Data/
USI_Laughs	[132]	34	17.6 %	22–37 (mean = 26.7)	Switzerland	Investigate the feasibility of recognizing laughter episodes using non-	Empatica e4	EDA, BVP, ACC, Temp	Three external raters voted the annotation of	Ten humorous YouTube videos (~10 min total) to elicit natural laughter	https://mcscs.inf.usi.ch/datase

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Dataset	Citation	N	Gender (% F)	Age	Location	Purpose	EDA device	Signals	Affective annotation	Stimuli	Link
						invasive wearable devices, aiming to enhance emotion-aware pervasive systems.			laughter episodes (laugh / not-laugh)		t/laughing-dataset/

\Note. ACC = triaxial accelerometer; BVP = blood volume pulse; PPG = photoplethysmography; ECG = electrocardiography; EDA = electrodermal activity; EEG = electroencephalography; EMG = electromyography; EOG = electro-oculography; HR = heart rate; N = number of participants; N/A = not available; Resp = respiration; Temp = temperature; SAM = Self-Assessment Manikin; SSSQ = Short Stress State Questionnaire; STAI = State-Trait Anxiety Inventory; PANAS = Positive and Negative Affect Schedule; TSST = Trier Social Stress Test; IAPS = International Affective Picture System.

3.2.7. Electrodermal activity (EDA)

Among the studies we reviewed, we identified 35 distinct EDA devices, with 6.6 % of studies employing custom-made devices. Shimmer, BioSemi ActiveTwo, Empatica and BIOPAC were the most used devices (see Fig. 6). On the other hand, 8.8 % of the studies did not report the specific device used or clarified whether it was a homemade solution.

Regarding the placement of electrodes, 52.6 % of studies reported the hemibody of placement (e.g., left, right, dominant, non-dominant), while 82.6 % reported the body part where they were set (e.g. hands, chest, wrist). When reported, the left side was preferred for electrode placement (53.5 %). The hands were the most common site for electrode placement (74 %), specifically in the middle (42.7 %) and index (42.3 %) fingers. Fig. 7 provides a detailed overview of electrode placement.

3.2.8. Model performance

Our analysis tracked the progression and distribution of affective models (dimensional or categorical), and algorithm types (classification or regression) used across studies. It is worth noting that affective models are used to conceptualize human emotions in either discrete categories (e.g., happiness, sadness, anger) or continuous dimensions (e.g., arousal, valence). Similarly, the types of algorithms can vary, with classification algorithms predicting discrete outcomes and regression algorithms predicting continuous outcomes.

Over time, we observed an initial preference for categorical models during the first five years (excluding 2012), followed by a shift towards a dominance of dimensional models (refer to Fig. 8A). Overall, dimensional models accounted for 72.1 % of all models used. Additionally, classification analysis clearly predominated the publication landscape, accounting for 93.7 % of the total number of models, whereas regression analysis was performed in a minority of publications (Fig. 8B).

Among the classification algorithms employed, support vector machines were the dominant algorithm by a significant margin, followed by tree-based models and k-nearest neighbors (Fig. 9A). On the regression side, decision tree models emerged by far as the most frequently used, followed by linear regression and convolutional neural networks (Fig. 9B).

An intriguing aspect we observed was the extent to which studies ventured into a psychological or physiological interpretation of their results, rather than limiting their discussion to the performance of the model. Out of 181 papers, only 69 offered such insights.

3.3. Meta-analysis

Our meta-analysis, conducted according to predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, analyzed 154 arousal models and an equal number of valence models from 35 different studies. A summary of the performance of the best emotion recognition models based on EDA from each study is provided in Table 2, which details the accuracies for arousal, valence, and the mean performance across different machine learning models and databases.

The analysis revealed a statistically significant advantage of arousal models over valence models (*Mean difference* = 2.42 %, 95 % CI [1.59 %, 5.21 %]; $p = 0.001$), as determined by permutation and bootstrap analyses. In addition, the Bland-Altman plot (see Fig. 10) showed a negative correlation between mean accuracy and the interdimensional performance difference (i.e., arousal–valence). This implies that as mean accuracy increases, the performance difference between arousal and valence tends to decrease.

To further investigate the factors influencing this performance gap, we conducted a regression analysis including model families, databases, and control variables. The expanded model showed significant explanatory power (OLS adj. $R^2 = 0.455$; $F(26, 127) = 5.910$, $p < 0.001$). Both ordinary least-squares and robust (Huber-T) specifications revealed several significant predictors. Among model families, Convolutional Neural Networks ($\beta = 6.77 \pm 3.13$, $p = 0.032$), Fully-connected Neural

Fig. 5. Emotion categories and dimensions most frequently predicted from EDA signals. (A) Most frequently modeled discrete categories. Bars show how many of the machine learning models extracted from the 181 reviewed articles attempted to recognize each emotion category. Colors are used for visual grouping only and have no analytical meaning. (B) Most frequently modeled dimensional constructs. Valence and arousal dominate, appearing in more than two-thirds of all models, while constructs such as flow or frustration are rarely addressed. (C) Category co-occurrence network. Nodes represent the categories in (A); edge thickness indicates the number of models that simultaneously predicted the two linked categories. (D) Dimensional co-occurrence network. Nodes represent the dimensions in (C). The thick valence–arousal edge reflects the canonical circumplex approach, while thinner links reveal less-studied combinations (e.g., engagement–predictability). Counts and edges are model-based, so totals may exceed the 181 articles reviewed.

Networks ($\beta = 7.79 \pm 2.42, p = 0.001$), Naive Bayes ($\beta = 6.50 \pm 3.11, p = 0.037$), and Support Vector Machines ($\beta = 6.01 \pm 2.49, p = 0.016$) showed significant positive effects on the performance gap, indicating that these architectures tend to produce higher accuracy for arousal compared to valence classification. Regarding database effects, K-Emo-Con ($\beta = -17.35 \pm 2.93, p < 0.001$) and ASCERTAIN ($\beta = -7.78 \pm 3.85, p = 0.043$) showed a significant negative effect, suggesting better performance in valence classification, while VREED ($\beta = 25.08 \pm 2.44, p < 0.001$) and DEAP ($\beta = 3.49 \pm 1.58, p = 0.027$) showed significant effects in the opposite direction, favoring arousal classification. Among the control variables, mean accuracy remained a significant negative predictor ($\beta = -0.13 \pm 0.06, p = 0.025$), while sample size and publication year were not significant predictors. These results suggest that both the choice of model architecture and the characteristics of the database significantly influence the arousal–valence performance gap, with some combinations leading to larger gaps and others to more

balanced performance between the two dimensions.

4. Discussion

In the present work, our objectives were twofold, as we conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis focusing on the confluence of affective science and affective computing in the context of emotion recognition systems using EDA. First, we sought to systematically review methodological aspects of 181 studies published between 2010 and 2025, such as emotion elicitation techniques and affective annotation tools. Second, we selected a subset of 154 pairs of arousal and valence models from 35 studies for meta-analysis according to our pre-specified inclusion and exclusion criteria. In the following sections, we discuss methodological considerations and qualitatively integrate these findings.

Fig. 6. Most frequently used EDA devices in emotion recognition research with EDA. Horizontal bars rank devices by the number of articles that employed them. Shimmer and BioSemi ActiveTwo lead the field, with Empatica and BIOPAC following. The “Others” bar groups devices mentioned only once.

Fig. 7. Electrode placement preferences in EDA-based emotion recognition studies. (A) Laterality: Sensors are most commonly placed on the left or nondominant side. (B) Body region: the hand is the primary site, with the wrist a distant second; “other” includes chest, ankle, arm, back, abdomen, and neck placements. (C) Finger selection within hand-mounted setups: index and middle fingers clearly dominate. Bars indicate the number of articles reporting each option.

4.1. Discrepancy between emotion modeling and machine learning approaches

This section aims to highlight a notable discrepancy in emotion recognition systems with EDA: although there is an increasing trend toward the use of dimensional models for affective variables like valence and arousal, the machine learning approaches employed in the field have not adapted in parallel to capture the continuous nature of these emotional dimensions.

Our analysis reveals a surge in the use of dimensional emotion models in the affective computing literature. This shift signifies a growing recognition of emotions as complex, multidimensional constructs, rather than discrete, categorical entities [61]. Simultaneously, our review sought to investigate whether this trend towards dimensional emotion modeling was mirrored by an increase in the adoption of regression models, an approach well-suited for capturing the continuous nature of emotional data. However, contrary to our expectations, we found that the use of regression models has not increased alongside the growing adoption of dimensional emotion models. Interestingly, this

pattern seems consistent with findings from other domains of emotion recognition research; Saganowski et al. [62] also observed in their comprehensive review of emotion recognition systems from physiological signals that there is a scarcity of studies tackling regression tasks, indicating that the preference for classification over regression extends beyond EDA signals to other peripheral physiological signals as well.

This discrepancy suggests a bias in the field towards simplifying dimensional emotional data into categories (e.g. “positive” or “negative”). Such simplification may not only be a performance optimization strategy but may also be driven by the specific application goals of the technologies being developed. For instance, a virtual agent designed to detect low valence in a user to generate a predefined response may require simplifying emotional data into more actionable categories.

However, if we want to use affective computing to better understand human affect, this tendency to categorize risks not only oversimplifies the nuanced nature of dimensional emotion constructs, but also fails to capture critical information useful for more accurate and representative modeling. By reducing dimensional data to categorical representations, we may inadvertently neglect important variations and subtleties

Fig. 8. Shifts in modeling choices over time in EDA-based emotion recognition studies (2010–2025). (A) Annual article counts split between categorical (blue) and dimensional (orange) emotion models. (B) Annual counts split between classification (blue) and regression (orange) algorithms. Stacked bars show the total number of studies published each year, revealing the tilt toward dimensional models in contrast to the continued dominance of classification approaches.

inherent in emotional experiences, therefore limiting the generalization of these models.

Our findings underscore the need for future research in affective computing to consciously balance the practical necessities of machine learning approaches with the conceptual richness of dimensional emotion models. As the field continues to evolve, it is critical that we strive for methods that not only optimize performance but also aim to understand the complex nature of affective states accurately.

4.2. The role of detailed methodologies and open databases in achieving replication

The fields of psychology and neuroscience, as documented in recent studies [63,64], confront substantial challenges in achieving replication, a fundamental aspect of scientific rigor. While these obstacles are not unique to these fields, they have received considerable attention in the broader scientific literature [65]. Our findings indicate that similar challenges are present within the field of affective computing. This subsection explores the complexities of achieving replication in EDA-based emotion recognition research, focusing on how methodological transparency and access to open databases can impact reproducibility. Specific areas of concern include the variability in reporting demographics, sensor placement, and emotion induction methods. Additionally, the limited use of open databases and the absence of standardized protocols across studies may contribute to difficulties in ensuring scientific reliability. Our findings suggest that addressing these areas could help strengthen the foundation for more reproducible research in affective computing.

First, a considerable number of the studies reviewed did not provide detailed information regarding their samples. For example, only about a quarter (27.6 %) disclosed the country of origin of the sample, a critical omission given the well-established influence of culture on emotional

experience [66–68]. In addition, important demographic data, such as sample size and age of participants, were often missing. Most notably, the absence of gender distribution is particularly troubling given existing research highlighting gender differences in emotional responses [69–71].

Second, open databases now account for 49.72 % of usages, yet almost half of the studies still rely exclusively on restricted resources. This practice severely diminishes the transparency and reproducibility foundational to scientific advancement [72,73]. Our observations align with Roy et al. [74], who pointed out the challenges in reproducing study findings due to the unavailability of data and code.

For those studies that do use open databases, there is a discernible concentration on a few select resources, with 89 % of the papers ($n = 80$) relying on just six pre-established datasets: DEAP, AMIGOS, MAHNOB-HCI, CASE, ASCERTAIN, and WESAD. This heavy reliance on a limited repertoire of sources further limits the variety of data used in EDA research.

Third, a significant lack of reporting concerns the use of physiological measures. Electrodermal activity (EDA) is a workhorse signal in affective-computing research, yet even the most elementary acquisition details are sometimes missing. Across the 181 studies in our review we identified 35 different devices—with Shimmer, BioSemi ActiveTwo, Empatica, and BIOPAC heading the list—and 6.6 % of articles relied on custom hardware. Most strikingly, almost one in ten papers (8.8 %) failed to name the device at all, exposing a critical gap in methodological transparency that hampers both reproducibility and the interpretation of sensor-level variability.

The larger gap concerns where the electrodes were placed. Almost half of the papers (47.4 %) do not specify the hemibody (left/right or dominant/non-dominant), and almost a fifth (17.4 %) omit the body site altogether. For those papers that do provide a location, the community overwhelmingly favors the hands (74 %), especially the middle (42.7 %)

Fig. 9. Algorithm popularity and accuracy in EDA-based emotion-recognition research. (A) Frequency with which each classification-model family ($n = 1033$ models, 181 studies) is used: support-vector machines, tree-based and k -nearest-neighbor approaches dominate. (B) Corresponding frequencies for regression models, where tree-based and linear models prevail. (C) Meta-analysis of $n = 154$ matched model pairs (35 studies) reporting binary arousal (blue) and valence (orange) accuracy: box-and-whisker plots show performance across model families.

and index (42.3 %) fingers of the left hand (53.5 %), a convention inherited from the public datasets underlying most benchmarks. This homogeneity, coupled with incomplete reporting, limits any meaningful assessment of how placement affects model performance.

A recent laboratory study by Shui et al. [75] illustrates the problem. Using simultaneous recordings from nine anatomical sites in 36 participants, they showed that a classifier combining all sites achieved 80.4 ± 8.1 % accuracy for high vs. low arousal and 76.4 ± 10.2 % for three-level valence, whereas the best single-site model based on wrist signals achieved only 60.9 % and 50.4 % (both improvements, $ps < .05$). In addition, wrist electrodes were most informative for valence, whereas ankle and lower abdominal sites better tracked arousal.

Based on these observations, we urge researchers to include three complementary details in any EDA protocol: (i) the exact body site of each electrode, (ii) the hemibody in which it is placed (left/right or dominant/non-dominant), and (iii) the participant's lateral dominance (handedness). Descriptions should be specific, e.g., "left palmar surface, middle phalanx of index finger" rather than simply "hand".

Documentation of both electrode laterality and participant handedness is critical because asymmetries in electrodermal reactivity have been associated with hemispheric differences in sympathetic control [26], [76–78]. By improving the transparency of device identification, electrode placement, and participant handedness, future datasets will allow robust meta-analytic tests of how these methodological factors modulate the accuracy of emotion recognition models.

Finally, there is a lack of standardization in the methods used to elicit emotions in most of the literature reviewed. While some variation in methods can be attributed to concerns about ecological validity [79], the lack of detailed reporting on elicitation techniques remains an area for improvement. Furthermore, 28.6 % of the studies failed to use or specify any self-report questionnaire, and an additional 5.9 % relied on instruments developed in other papers, which are essential for precise emotion prediction [80]. Without uniform elicitation protocols and transparency regarding the use of self-report methods, the effectiveness of emotion induction in subjects cannot be reliably assessed. This way, without these data, it is not possible to quantitatively evaluate how

Table 2

Binary arousal/valence classification accuracy of EDA-based emotion recognition models (ordered by mean accuracy, highest → lowest).

Citation	Year	Machine Learning Model	Database	Arousal Accuracy (%)	Valence Accuracy (%)	Mean Accuracy (%)
[133]	2023	MobileNet-CNN (depthwise separable convolutions classify scalogram-transformed EDA signals with extremely low latency during inference)	AMIGOS	98.39	99.19	98.79
[134]	2024	Transformer + ANN (federated transformer encoders feed lightweight ANN, protecting data privacy across devices during training)	AMIGOS	86.15	85.80	85.98
[112]	2017	Random Forest (bagged decision trees model EMD-derived features)	DEAP	81.81	89.29	85.55
[135]	2021	SVM (RBF/Gaussian kernel maps extracted features into high-dimensional space for optimal margin separation)	AMIGOS	85.75	84.50	85.12
[136]	2024	XGBoost (gradient-boosted decision trees with automatic importance pruning efficiently select salient EDA predictors)	VREED	92.32	77.01	84.66
[137]	2023	Lightweight CNN + Bi-GRU (spectrogram CNN embeddings temporally refined by bidirectional GRU accurately capture EDA dynamics)	AMIGOS	83.00	81.00	82.00
[138]	2023	Feed-forward NN (fully connected layers with spectrogram features)	K-EmoCon	69.62	93.32	81.47
[139]	2022	ELM (single hidden-layer network learns statistical and VGG-16 spectrogram features with minimal training time)	AMIGOS	80.94	80.63	80.79
[140]	2022	Residual Temporal and Channel Attention Group (RTCAG; 1D-CNN backbone plus attention modules model channels and temporal context for richer feature representations)	AMIGOS	83.42	77.15	80.29
[141]	2022	MLP (three-layer perceptron uses SF-GARG statistical and demographic graph embeddings for personalized emotion inference)	DEAP	80.20	79.30	79.75
[142]	2023	DDQ-RL (double deep Q-learning selects FOX-optimized features and updates policy for balanced classification rewards)	ASCERTAIN	78.96	79.52	79.24
[143]	2022	Random Forest (ensemble evaluates selected time, frequency, entropy attributes to output interpretable arousal valence labels)	ASCERTAIN	77.30	80.50	78.90
[144]	2021	Logistic Regression (linear model on PCA-reduced recurrence plots offers transparent baseline for emotion decoding)	AMIGOS	79.10	78.20	78.65
[145]	2024	ConvLSTM (two convolutional layers extract spatial patterns feeding LSTM units that capture temporal dependencies)	BM-SWU	76.65	80.21	78.43
[113]	2019	HDC-MER (hyperdimensional encoding fuses spatial and temporal cues into high-dimensional binary vectors for classification)	AMIGOS	69.40	82.20	75.80
[146]	2024	Random Forest (recursive feature elimination prunes irrelevant predictors before training ensemble decision trees)	CASE	79.79	71.71	75.75
[114]	2019	MLP (PCA-aggregated temporal, frequency, window features drive multi-layer perceptron for integrated emotion estimation)	DEAP	79.00	69.80	74.40
[115]	2020	1D-CNN (time, frequency, time-frequency inputs processed by convolutional stacks with batch normalization and SGD optimization)	DEAP	75.00	72.00	73.50
[116]	2019	DCNN (deep convolution and pooling layers hierarchically extract abstraction levels from raw EDA sequences)	AMIGOS	71.00	75.00	73.00
[147]	2021	SVM (RBF/Gaussian kernel maps extracted features into high-dimensional space for optimal margin separation)	VREED	87.50	56.25	71.88
[117]	2016	Random Forest (ensemble uses statistical features across multiple time windows to stabilize prediction variance)	DEAP	71.46	71.04	71.25
[118]	2020	SDBN (spiking deep belief network with LIF neurons models temporal spikes, mimicking neuromorphic processing)	DEAP	72.08	68.90	70.49
[119]	2020	M1D-CNN (multiscale one-dimensional convolutions capture patterns at various resolutions within EDA signal segments)	DEAP	69.33	71.43	70.38
[148]	2021	k-NN (instance-based classifier searches nearest neighbors among time domain features)	Private	55.55	74.07	64.81
[149]	2023	SVM (TEAP features exploits transform encoding for compact yet discriminative representation)	DEAP	64.40	65.10	64.75
[120]	2018	ELM (fast single-layer network trained on eight statistical descriptors for quick emotion predictions)	AMIGOS	63.28	64.84	64.06
[150]	2023	EmotionNet-Student (GSR convolutional head plus stacked transformers fused by heterogeneity-based depth fusion for unimodal classification)	DEAP	55.06	69.18	62.12
[151]	2022	CNN (four 1D convolutional layers and max-pooling produce softmax probabilities over emotional classes)	DEAP	62.50	60.18	61.34
[152]	2022	MLP (fully connected network consumes 1D-CNN encoded features to output arousal and valence labels)	MAHNOB-HCI	60.50	60.55	60.52
[121]	2020	Hybrid 1D-CNN + Bi-GRU (convolutional feature extractor followed by residual bidirectional GRU captures spatial temporal dependencies)	PMEmo	60.22	60.66	60.44
[153]	2024	Random Forest (ensemble of 200 trees learns statistical predictors)	Private	57.70	61.60	59.65
[154]	2022	DCNN (three stacked 1D convolutions with global average pooling learn directly from raw EDA waveforms)	Private	58.30	55.60	56.95
[122]	2019	Res-SISubnet (ResNet-18 extracts features from tonic, phasic, original components generated via CvxEDA decomposition)	PMEmo	57.24	55.92	56.58
[123]	2016	SVM (RBF/Gaussian kernel)	MAHNOB-HCI	62.23	50.52	56.38
[155]	2024	SVM	DEAP	57.50	55.00	56.25

Note. Binary arousal (low ↔ high activation) and valence (negative ↔ positive affect) classification from electrodermal activity (EDA). Rows are ordered by this value. Acronyms: CNN = convolutional neural network (1D-CNN, DCNN = one-dimensional, deep variants; MobileNet-CNN uses depth-wise separable convolutions); Transformer = attention-based encoder architecture; ANN/NN = artificial neural network; SVM = support vector machine (RBF/Gaussian = radial-basis-function kernel); RF = random forest; XGBoost = extreme gradient boosting; ELM = extreme learning machine; MLP = multilayer perceptron; LSTM/GRU/Bi-GRU = (long short-term/gated recurrent) units; ConvLSTM = convolutional LSTM; DDQ-RL = double deep-Q reinforcement learning; EMD = empirical mode decomposition; PCA = principal-component analysis; GAP = global average pooling; SDBN/LIF = spiking deep belief network with leaky-integrate-and-fire neurons; M1D-CNN

= multiscale 1D-CNN; k-NN = k -nearest-neighbor. Public EDA corpora: AMIGOS, DEAP, VREED, ASCERTAIN, K-EmoCon, BM-SWU, CASE, MAHNOB-HCI, PMEmo. Citations [112]–[155] correspond to the manuscript reference list.

Fig. 10. Comparative accuracy of arousal and valence decoding models. Each marker is a paired model from one study ($n = 154$). The x-axis indicates the model's accuracy in classifying high vs. low valence; the y-axis indicates the difference in accuracy (arousal–valence). Points above zero indicate that arousal was predicted more accurately than valence. Triangles indicate models trained on the DEAP benchmark, circles all other datasets; colors indicate the source of the study (legend, right). The solid horizontal line marks the mean difference (+2.42%), and the dashed lines show its 95% confidence limits, highlighting a consistent, albeit small, advantage in arousal detection.

different application scenarios influence the performance of predictive models of emotions.

4.3. Limited use of theoretical frameworks

A significant issue encountered during our review can be described as the adoption of a theoretically "neutral" stance or "agnostic approach" in the field of affective computing. This phenomenon refers to studies on emotions conducted without explicit attention or consideration to the theoretical foundations that underpin emotion elicitation and recognition. Our review suggests that there is a noticeable gap between technical and theoretical perspectives, with a strong emphasis on applied approaches that may at times overlook critical psychological and physiological interpretations. In this subsection, we discuss the value of integrating both predictive and explanatory models to enhance the interpretability and applicability of emotion recognition. Furthermore, we point out issues related to the inconsistent categorization of emotional states, noting that more consistent use of self-reports and standardized labeling methods could support the theoretical

advancement of the field.

In particular, we found that most articles originate from technical and engineering-oriented journals rather than those focused on psychology or neuroscience. This disciplinary divide is significant because it suggests that studies targeting a technical audience might not fully account for the psychological and physiological underpinnings of emotion recognition. The predominance of technical discourse raises crucial questions about the synergy between predictive models and traditional explanatory frameworks in psychology and neuroscience. While explanatory models aim to illuminate the causal dynamics within data, predictive models excel at discerning patterns within complex and high-dimensional datasets, thereby offering a complementary perspective that enhances generalizability and the discovery of subtle, underlying relationships [81], [82].

To take full advantage of affective computing research, it will be crucial to adopt an integrated methodology that combines the predictive power of computational models with the rich theoretical insights of explanatory frameworks. However, for predictive models to be truly informative about emotional experience, they should be interpretable.

Our review reveals a notable deficiency in this area: of 181 papers reviewed, only 69 attempted to interpret the results in terms of physiological or psychological implications, suggesting a significant gap in the literature. A serious effort to synthesize predictive power with the interpretability necessary for physiological and psychological analysis will enable us to better understand and replicate the complexity of human emotion through advanced artificial intelligence models.

Another important concern relates to the selection of emotional categories and dimensions analyzed. Many of the studies reviewed omitted the use of self-report measures and delegated the responsibility for categorizing affective states solely to the researcher, depending on the chosen emotion elicitation methods, which were often ad hoc. This raises critical questions about the validity of emotional labeling; for example, can we reliably distinguish whether an emotion labeled "amusement" is really amusement and not joy or happiness? Beyond potential distortions of emotion categories, certain categories were entirely missing in the reviewed studies. It is imperative that future studies not only use self-report measures to validate emotional states, but also adopt a more rigorous and theoretically informed approach to the selection of emotional categories and dimensions. Without addressing these fundamental issues, we risk perpetuating uncertainties that undermine the development of the field, possibly due to a lack of closer cross-disciplinary collaboration between psychology and computer science disciplines [83].

4.4. Arousal models outperform valence in EDA-based emotion recognition

Our meta-analysis of 154 arousal models and an equal number of valence models across 35 unique studies provides valuable insights into their comparative performance in emotion recognition: our data suggest that arousal models outperform valence models with EDA. The relatively higher accuracy of arousal models could be attributed to several factors. One possibility is that arousal, which is by definition associated with physiological activation, may manifest more noticeably in autonomic signals, thereby facilitating its detection by machine learning models using EDA [84]. Another possible explanation relates to the type of stimuli used in the studies included in our analysis. Certain types of stimuli, such as images or sounds, may be more likely to elicit strong arousal responses than distinct valence responses, leading to greater accuracy in arousal models [85]. Future research would benefit from investigating the potential effects of different stimulus types, including their low and high-level properties, on the performance of arousal and valence models.

The observed negative correlation between mean accuracy and the difference in accuracy (arousal–valence) is striking, especially at lower levels of mean accuracy. This significant performance gap at lower levels could indicate that arousal models are performing significantly better than chance levels, while valence models are struggling to do so at a lower level of combined performance (close to 50 % accuracy). This could indicate that one dimension is being modeled effectively while the other is not. The more pronounced difference may be due to the inherent characteristics of the arousal dimension, which may be more easily captured by physiological signals such as EDA. For example, the convex optimization approach to EDA processing (cvxEDA) proposed by Greco et al. [86] has become a common preprocessing step in machine learning pipelines dealing with EDA, which allows estimation of autonomic nervous system activity from the EDA signal. Phasic component peaks obtained from cvxEDA have been found to correlate with different levels of arousal, providing a robust method for quantifying arousal [86]. Such preprocessing methods enhance the detection capabilities of arousal models by refining the input data for subsequent machine learning algorithms.

Alternatively, performance discrepancies between arousal and valence models could arise from other methodological choices, such as feature engineering and selection, that inadvertently favor the detection

of one emotional dimension over the other, again highlighting the importance of theoretically informed methodological choices in affective computing research.

This naturally leads to a second question, does the choice of algorithmic family further modulate the arousal–valence gap, or is the effect largely independent of the classifier used? To examine this, we aggregated the accuracy scores of the 154 machine-learning models and grouped them into the ten broad families shown in Fig. 9C and Table 2. Our regression analysis reveals significant differences in how different model families affect the arousal–valence gap. Specifically, Convolutional Neural Networks, Fully-connected Neural Networks, Naive Bayes, and Support Vector Machines show significant positive effects on the gap, suggesting that these architectures tend to produce larger differences between arousal and valence classification performance. However, these effects must be interpreted in conjunction with the database being used, as our analysis reveals strong interactions between model families and databases. For instance, while neural network architectures generally show positive effects on the gap, their impact varies significantly across different databases. These findings underscore the need for harmonized benchmarking frameworks and cross-dataset validations before firm conclusions can be drawn about the "best" model architecture for EDA-based emotion recognition.

Furthermore, as models improve in overall accuracy, the performance gap appears to narrow. However, models with extremely high mean accuracy seem to be outliers and should be interpreted with caution. Given the exploratory nature of our study and its reliance on a limited dataset, these observations should be considered preliminary findings that highlight the need for more extensive research to understand the factors contributing to these trends.

Our robust regression analysis further reveals that the choice of database significantly influences the arousal–valence gap, with some databases (e.g. K-EmoCon) showing smaller gaps and others (e.g. VREED and DEAP) showing larger gaps. This suggests that dataset characteristics play a crucial role in determining the relative performance of arousal and valence classification, potentially more so than the choice of model architecture. These findings emphasize the importance of considering database-specific factors when developing and evaluating emotion recognition models.

The superior performance of arousal models, as suggested by our meta-analysis, points to areas for further research to enhance the accuracy of valence models. This could involve refining feature selection methods, testing more suitable machine learning algorithms, or incorporating multimodal data sources that may provide a richer context for predicting valence.

In conclusion, our meta-analysis provides empirical evidence to the field of affective computing by illuminating the comparative efficacy of arousal and valence models in emotion recognition. As the field moves forward, delving into the specific complexities and nuanced differences of different affective dimensions, as well as understanding the impact of database characteristics, will be critical to further advancing the predictive capabilities and ecological validity of emotion recognition models.

4.5. Generalizability of emotion recognition research requires cultural and geographical representation

Generalizability is a cornerstone of scientific research, vital for ensuring reproducibility and broad applicability. In emotion recognition research, particularly using EDA, the geographical and cultural diversity of study samples is crucial [26]. Our systematic review reveals a concentration of research within Asian countries, notably China, India, and Turkey, with significant contributions from the United States and Europe. However, regions like Latin America and Africa are markedly underrepresented.

This geographical and cultural bias extends to dataset compositions, often overlooking diverse racial and ethnic groups. Such limitations are

not unique to our field but reflect a broader trend in human-centric research [87]. The predominance of data from Asian contexts could impair the applicability of emotion recognition models across varied cultural and racial backgrounds. This concern is echoed in recent studies [85], highlighting the need for more inclusive research practices.

Expanding datasets geographically is vital for enhancing research generalizability. Recent trends show an increase in testing machine learning models' transferability across diverse datasets [88], [89], [90], emphasizing the need for more inclusive research in underrepresented regions. Future research that embraces this diversity will support the development of conclusions that are more generalizable and methodologically robust.

4.6. Recent advances in EDA-based emotion recognition

In recent years, significant efforts have been made to apply deep learning techniques to improve emotion recognition systems based on EDA. These methods have begun to address critical limitations associated with feature engineering and limited labeled data, which have historically constrained the development of affective computing systems. Specifically, the application of automated feature extraction and self-supervised learning has emerged as a response to these challenges.

One interesting attempt is the work by Ganapathy et al. [91], who proposed a multiscale convolutional neural network (MSCNN) that directly processes raw EDA signals. By capturing high-level features across multiple scales, the MSCNN aims to reduce reliance on extensive preprocessing. However, results have demonstrated limited effectiveness in arousal and valence detection (e.g., Area Under the ROC Curve [AUROC] scores around 0.50). This indicates that substantial modifications or further analysis (potentially testing with other datasets) are needed to test whether this approach is effective across both affective dimensions.

In another attempt to improve emotion recognition using wearable biosignal data, Wu et al. [92] proposed a self-supervised learning (SSL) framework for wearable emotion recognition. Their approach focuses on leveraging SSL to overcome the limitations of traditional fully-supervised approaches, particularly overfitting due to limited labeled data. They conducted an ablation study specifically on electrodermal activity (EDA), along with other modalities, to explore performance in emotion recognition tasks. The results indicated that EDA performed particularly well in detecting arousal states, outperforming other modalities in unimodal settings. This demonstrates the potential of SSL in enhancing the effectiveness of EDA-based emotion recognition, especially when labeled data is scarce.

Similarly, Perry Fordson et al. [93] expanded the capabilities of deep learning models by incorporating gender and age information through the Gender-Age Relation Graph to enhance emotion classification from EDA data. Their approach used a weighted fusion of these demographic embeddings with EDA statistical features, showing an improvement in valence and arousal recognition accuracy of 2–3% on the DEAP dataset compared to traditional models. This emphasizes the value of demographic-aware models in improving the performance of affective computing systems.

In addition to advances in modeling approaches, the development of new datasets has also contributed to progress in EDA-based emotion recognition. Recently released datasets, such as CASE [16], POPANE [94], and EMAP [95], have emphasized continuous, real-time emotion annotations. CASE, for instance, includes real-time emotional labels during video viewing, which supports time-sensitive analyses of affective responses. Similarly, POPANE provides an extensive dataset of continuously recorded psychophysiological responses from 895 participants, capturing a range of emotional states. EMAP offers a dataset of 145 individuals' reactions to emotion-provoking film clips, including moment-by-moment ratings for emotional arousal along with overall and categorical ratings. These datasets enable the development of models that can capture the inherently dynamic nature of emotions.

Another promising advancement involves incorporating physiological knowledge directly into predictive models to enhance interpretability. Ghiasi et al. [96] proposed the Physiologically-Informed Gaussian Process (PhGP) model, which integrates physiological principles as priors within a Bayesian framework. By aligning model predictions with established physiological knowledge, the PhGP model not only improves predictive performance but also enhances the interpretability of the results—a key consideration for the practical application of emotion recognition systems in areas such as healthcare and human-computer interaction.

In summary, recent developments in EDA-based emotion recognition represent a significant shift in the field, characterized by the integration of deep learning techniques, the emergence of new datasets that account for the continuous nature of emotions, and a focus on model interpretability. These advances contribute to improving both the accuracy and generalizability of emotion recognition systems while enhancing our understanding of the link between emotional states and physiological signals. By advancing model performance and interpretability, these innovations pave the way for more robust and practical applications in affective computing, and, from an affective science perspective, deepen our understanding of the interplay between emotions and physiological responses, effectively bridging computational and psychological approaches.

4.7. Limitations

The scope of this work is primarily influenced by the nature of our sample. We acknowledge that certain conditions of our review may limit the breadth of our conclusions. It is important to clarify that our decision to exclude articles using a multimodal approach to emotion prediction [97], [98], [99] was driven by our focus on the EDA literature, given the close relationship between EDA and arousal as an affective dimension. While this focus allows for a deep dive into the EDA literature, it necessarily neglects other potentially informative signals, such as ECG or pupillometry, that may provide complementary or even superior insights into arousal. Thus, future iterations of this work might consider expanding the review to include these other unimodal signals or even multimodal approaches. Such an expansion could provide a more nuanced understanding of the relationship between different branches of peripheral nervous system activity and affective components such as arousal. For readers interested in the broader domain of physiological signals, especially in the context of wearable technology, the work of Saganowski et al. [62] offers comprehensive insights that could greatly complement the findings of this review.

Finally, articles studying clinical populations were intentionally excluded, as our goal was to explore the basic study of affective states at the event level—specifically, the prediction of different affective states within the same subject. In contrast, clinical studies typically aim to detect mood alterations, such as anxiety or depression, relative to healthy control subjects, thus, shifting the focus of analysis to the subject level (between subjects) rather than the event level (within subjects). While subject-level studies of arousal and emotion are critical for developing biomarkers in support of novel therapeutics, they did not fit in the scope of this work. However, given the evidence on the influence of mental states on electrodermal activity [100], [101], we would expect that modeling stimulus-induced modulation of arousal and emotion may hold a key to clinical applications by, potentially, uncovering differences in processing affective stimuli that are characteristic for certain groups of patients.

4.8. Recommendations

Through our exploration of affective computing models, we have identified several critical practices that can improve the transparency, reproducibility, and overall quality of research in this field. These recommendations cover various aspects of the research process, including

data transparency and accessibility, sample characteristics, methodological clarity, cultural and theoretical considerations, performance metrics, data analysis sharing, and study pre-registration. We have summarized these key recommendations in Table 3: "Best-practice checklist for transparent and reproducible affective-computing research".

Following these recommendations can help researchers ensure that their work is conducted with the utmost rigor, thereby enhancing its credibility and facilitating meaningful advances in the field. For additional guidance, particularly on physiological measures, researchers should consult Behnke et al. [102], who provide a checklist for responsible wearable use in affective research. Taken together, these guidelines can serve as a valuable resource for those already engaged in affective computing research and for those considering entering this burgeoning field.

Table 3

Best-practice checklist for transparent and reproducible affective-computing research.

Focus area	Recommended practice
Data Transparency and Accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide open access to the study data to facilitate replication. • Ensure a clear description of the data, indicating if the entire dataset or a subset was used, and which signals were incorporated.
Study Preregistration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preregister hypothesis-driven research to avoid Hypothesizing After the Results are Known (HARKing).
Sample Properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advocate for including diverse demographics for improved validity. • Provide a thorough account of sample properties (age range, gender distribution, geographical origin). • Discuss the impact of demographic details on study outcomes.
Methodology Clarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide detailed descriptions of emotion elicitation techniques and measurement methods. • Use validated self-report instruments to assess affective experience. • Discuss limitations or potential problems with the methods used.
Theoretical Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarify the theoretical framework guiding the study. • Specify examined affective states and the rationale behind their choice.
Cultural Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Account for the influence of cultural differences and social constructs on emotion studies. • Explain how cultural variations were managed in your study.
Baseline and Performance Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include a state-of-the-art baseline or compare findings with dummy models (i.e., basic prediction models that do not learn from data but use simple strategies, such as predicting the most frequent class or the mean of the target variable). • Report multiple performance metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, AUC-ROC). • Include a confusion matrix for detailed analysis of model predictions in classification studies.
Data Analysis Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make data analysis publicly accessible, including scripts, code, and computational procedures. • Use version control tools like Git for script and code development. • Publish in a public repository with detailed documentation for replicability.
Interpretability and Physiological Implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relate results to the broader affective science literature. • Analyze results from psychological and/or physiological perspectives to enrich understanding of affective phenomena.

4.9. Conclusion

This study sets out to explore affective and machine learning models and EDA measures used in affective computing literature. Our findings highlighted key areas for improvement in scientific practice, particularly in relation to data transparency and reporting. A recurring observation was the lack of a comprehensive psychophysiological interpretation of the findings.

Thus, we emphasize the importance of a psychological perspective in the study of emotions, in addition to the computational and statistical methods employed in affective computing. While the latter offers exciting new avenues for emotion research, a concerted effort to synergize affective science with affective computing is essential. Affective computing has already benefited from the affect-elicitation techniques employed in affective science, and conversely, affective science has adopted the measurement approaches of affective computing [103]. However, while the field of affective computing is emerging as a distinctly interdisciplinary field, recent evidence suggests that collaboration and cross-fertilization between scientists from different disciplines (e.g., psychologists and computer scientists) remains the exception rather than the rule in affective computing and affective science [83].

By fostering interdisciplinarity, we can significantly enhance the quality and robustness of our models, leading to a more holistic and nuanced understanding of affective phenomena. Furthermore, by generating models that are more physiologically valid, we can achieve superior developments in affective computing [104]. Artificial intelligence models that better represent the generative mechanisms of affective states will thus generalize more effectively when implemented in practical applications. This integrated approach also lays the groundwork for future research, as it will be pivotal in addressing identified gaps and advancing the field.

Supplementary Material

Supplementary material for this article is available online in a GitHub repository (<https://github.com/tomdamelio/review-emotion-recognition-eda>).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tomás Ariel D'Amelio: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Lorenzo Ariel Galán:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Emmanuel Alesandro Maldonado:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Agustín Ariel Díaz Barquintero:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Jerónimo Rodríguez Cuello:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing. **Nicolás Marcelo Bruno:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation. **Enzo Tagliacruzchi:** Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Denis-Alexander Engemann:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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Data availability

Supplementary material for this article is available online in a GitHub repository (<https://github.com/tomdamelio/review-emotion-recognition-eda>).

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